

1 Phytic acid as a biomass flame retardant for 2 Polyrotaxane based phase change materials

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10 **ABSTRACT.** Petrochemical resources are facing depletion and human long-term survival needs
11 sustainable development. In this era, it is very important to develop new sustainable phase change
12 materials (PCMs), because it has shown great application value in the effective utilization of industrial
13 waste heat, solar energy harvesting, and electronic heat treatment. In this work, we reported a biomass
14 phytic acid (PA) modified polyrotaxane (PLR) as PCMs for thermal management. The tensile
15 performances, fire safety, phase transition performances of the PCMs were investigated. It is found that
16 all the tensile properties, char residual, and fire-safety of PLR can be enhanced remarkably by introduce
17 of PA. Typically, the Young's modulus, yielding strength and tensile strength of the PLR were 826.7
18 MPa, 14.2 MPa and 14.2 MPa, respectively, and significantly increased to 1527.4 MPa, 22.1 MPa, and
19 24.0 MPa respectively, with the addition of 10 wt.% of PA. Elongation (>783 %) for all modified PCMs
20 was gradually increased with the increase of PA contents. Thermal analysis shows that the fire safety of

21 PLR is significantly improved. Specifically, for the best sample PLR-PA30, the pHRR could decrease
22 by 54.2 %, THR decreased by 34.0%; and the LOI increased from 20.8% to 28.2%. The PCMs showed
23 the perfect form stability and leakage-proof performance, enhanced thermal conductivity and
24 outstanding cycle properties. Notably, its biomass source, and high flexibility, enhanced fire safety and
25 completely green pathway may provide a practical way for the highly flexible and sustainable packaging
26 of electronic devices for heat treatment.

27 **KEYWORDS:** Polyrotaxane, Phase change materials, Phytic acid, Biomass, Shape memory materials

28

29 1. INTRODUCTION

30 Bill Gates recently pointed out that climate warming will be a global disaster that may be more extensive,
31 serious and far-reaching than the COVID-19. In order to avoid disaster, reverence and awe of nature is
32 a life attitude everyone should have; low carbon emission and sustainable development need to be the
33 primary concern of material scientists and chemists; and clean energy, green chemistry and
34 environmental protection manufacturing should be our preferred scientific proposition and main
35 direction. Phase change materials (PCMs) have attracted more and more attention recently in the
36 corresponding field of thermal regulation [1, 2] energy saving, harvesting and storage. [3-5] Nowadays,
37 PCMs involving high melting enthalpy have been applied for heat regulation of electronic devices. [6,
38 7] However, it is still a big challenge to apply PCMs conveniently because of their solid rigidity nature
39 and leakage problem. Considerable strategies have been dedicated to prepare flexible PCMs by blending
40 PCMs substances with some other flexible polymers. [8-10] The design and preparation of intrinsically
41 flexible PCM films are also well explored. [11] With the further development of 5G technology, the
42 amount of PCMs requests for both smart heat regulation and the safety concerns increases. However,
43 the organic PCMs are easily flammable, e.g., PEG and paraffin. The fire safety is still the main limitation
44 for the practical applications of organic PCMs. Thus, it is imperative to improve the fire safety for
45 advanced PCMs.

46 Nowadays, introducing flame retardants into PCMs is a most widely used pathway to enhance the
47 flame retardancy of PCMs. [12-17] On the other aspect, some renewable resources like DNA, [18, 19]
48 chitosan, [20] soy protein, [21] starch, [22] and phytic acid (PA) [23-25] have been widely applied as
49 sustainable flame retardants in the past decades. PA, an eco-friendly molecule, is biocompatible,
50 biodegradable, nontoxic, and phosphorus-rich (28 wt.%). [26] Thus it has been widely used as a bio-

51 based flame retardant for polymers. [27, 28] For examples, the double coatings (i.e., layer-by-layer self-
52 assembly) by varied combinations of egg white protein and PA were explored to flame retard cotton
53 fabrics. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) in air show that the char residues increases up to 32.9 wt.%
54 at 600 °C, which is obviously superior to the results of literature reports with other flame retardants.
55 [24]

56 Polyrotaxane (PLR) is a new type of flexible and intelligent multifunctional PCM. [29] It performed
57 excellent flexibility, mechanical strength and shape memory properties, thermoplastic properties, and
58 easy to be fabricated and functionalized. [30] It has significant practical significance to further develop
59 its applications.[31] As known, PLR is prepared in water. To realize good dispersion, water soluble,
60 eco-friendly flame retardant is a good choice. Furthermore, it is reported the liquid-like modifier can
61 act as an inter-pore bridge for a more homogeneous stress distribution, which ensures high mechanical
62 properties. [32] It is reported that the introduce of multiple hydrogen bonds into polymer system may
63 enhance the mechanical properties. [33-35] Therefore, we will use PA liquid as the flame retardant
64 modifier directly, and use it as acid source to prepare flame retardant PLR based PCMs.

65 Above all, we will prepare the PLRs according to our previous report and use PA as a flame retardant,
66 in order to obtain the PCM with enhanced tensile properties and FR performance, and promote its
67 practical application accordingly. The tensile properties, fire-safety, shape memory properties and phase
68 transition performance of the composites will be investigated and explore the potential applications of
69 the PCMs in thermal management of electronic devices.

70 2. EXPERIMENTAL

71 *Materials.* Poly (ethylene oxide) (PEO) with a weight average molar mass of $9 \times 10^5 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$, α -
72 Cyclodextrin (α -CD, $\geq 99.8\%$) and phytic acid (PA, 50 wt.%) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (USA)
73 and used without further treatment. Deionized water is made in our laboratory.

74 *Synthesis of polyrotaxane (PLR).* PEO (3 g) was dissolved in H₂O (80 mL) at 80 °C, and then α -CD (0.9
75 g) with different mass ratio 30% was slowly added. After stirring for overnight at room temperature,
76 the reaction mixture was cooled down and kept at 4 °C for 72 h to yield the corresponding inclusion
77 complex solutions.

78 *Preparation of PA modified PLR (PLR-PA) films.* The aqueous **PLR-PA** (with different contents of PA)
79 and pure PLR solution were casted directly into $10 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$ Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) mold. After
80 evaporation at room temperature, the flexible films (PLR (sample without PA), PLR-PA10
81 (PLR/PA=100/10 (w/w)), PLR-P20 (PLR/PA=100/20 (w/w)) and PLR-PA30 (PLR/PA=100/30 (w/w)))
82 were further dried under 100 °C for 6 h to remove the water. Finally, the films with thickness at about
83 0.1 mm were obtained by hot press (R-320 22015, QIEN, Wuhan, China, 150 °C, 10-20 MPa, 5 min).

84 *XRD* patterns of the films were recorded in reflection mode using a X'PERT-PRO diffractometer with
85 Cu K α ($\lambda=0.1542 \text{ nm}$) and Ni filter.

86 *ATR-FTIR* spectra of the films were recorded from 500 cm^{-1} to 4000 cm^{-1} using Jasco FT/IR-6100 at
87 room temperature.

88 *DSC* test was performed by using a TA-Q200 in a N₂ atmosphere (50 mL min^{-1}). The crystallinity ($\varphi_c \%$)
89 were calculated in the second heating run from -60 °C to 100 °C at heating rate of 10 °C min^{-1} by the
90 equation:

$$91 \quad \varphi_c \% = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\omega_i \Delta H_m^0} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

92 where, ΔH_m (J g^{-1}) represented the measured enthalpies of melting, ΔH_m^0 (J g^{-1}) was the melting
93 enthalpy for a complete crystalline polymer and ω_i was the weight content of the component i in the
94 sample. The ΔH_m^0 of PEO was 196.4 J g^{-1} .

95 *Cycle stability test.* Sample PLR-PA10 was selected for cycle stability test (100 cycles). Both heating
96 and cooling procedures were run from $-10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ to calculate the change of
97 exothermic and endothermic heat as well as the enthalpy efficiency and phase change temperatures.

98 *UV-Vis Absorption Spectrometry.* A UV-2600 (SHIMADZU Corp., Kyoto, Japan) spectrophotometer
99 was used for the determination of UV-vis transmittance spectra for the film with thickness at 0.1 mm .

100 *TGA* of the films was performed using a TGA in air atmosphere from $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$
101 using a TA-Q50 instrument.

102 *Form stability.* The sample was cut into a disc of $13.50 \pm 0.05 \text{ mm}$ with a cutter, and then heated at
103 different temperatures ($30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) for the detecting of form stability (leakage or shape change).

104 SEM and EDS were carried out on the apparatus (SEM, EVO MA15, Zeiss) and FIB-FEG SEM dual-
105 beam microscope (Helios NanoLab 600i, FEI).

106 *Tensile test.* The tensile test samples were dogbone-shaped, following with ISO 527-2 (1996) standard.

107 An Instron 5966 (USA) universal tensile testing machine was utilized at a rate of $50 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$.

108 Minimum 5 specimens were tested for each sample to obtain a reliable average value and standard
109 deviations.

110 *Fire resistance.* Samples with diameter of 13.5 mm were sent to the top of a flame, and a camera was
111 used to record combustion process.

112 *The fire behavior.* The fire behavior was investigated by cone calorimeter test according to ISO5660

113 (heat flux is $35 \text{ kW} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$). Limiting oxygen index (LOI) test was performed based on standard ASTM D

114 2863-77. The vertical burning test was carried on UL-94 vertical flame chamber according to ASTM
115 D3801.

116 *Thermal conductivity.* Thermal conductivity measurements were performed using a thermal constants
117 analyzer (TPS2500 S, Hot Disk) at room temperature. The sample is with thickness of ~4 mm.

118 *Shape Memory performance.* Each sample was cut from a film with dimensions 30 mm ×2.5 mm ×0.1
119 mm. The percentage of shape fixing ratio (R_f), and shape recovery (R_r), were calculated according to
120 the following equations:

$$121 \quad R_f(N) = \frac{l_f(N) - l_i(N-1)}{l_p(N) - l_i(N-1)} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

$$122 \quad R_r(N) = \frac{l_p(N) - l_r(N)}{l_p(N) - l_i(N-1)} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

123 where l_p was the length before releasing the applied load, l_f was the length obtained after releasing the
124 applied load, l_i was the initial sample length, and l_r was the final length after heating with no applied
125 load. N is the cycle number. Three cycles were included in the test, namely, C1, C2 and C3.

126 3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

127 3.1 Preparation and characterization of PLR-PA

128

129 **Fig. 1.** (a) PLR-PAs fabrication route by solvent blending casting, (b) UV-Vis spectra of PLR and PLR-PAs, (c)

130 SEM cross section image of PLR-PA30; (d) illustration of PA dispersion; (e) EDX mapping of C, P and O element,

131 (f) FTIR spectra of PLR and PLR-PAs and (g) XRD curves of the four samples.

132

133 PLR-30% with high form stability and melting enthalpy was synthesized according to our previous

134 work [29] and selected as reference in current work for evaluation of PA effect on the systematic

135 performance on the PLR-30%. The biomass PA (**Fig. 1a**) is blended directly with the PLR by using

136 solvent casting method, for obtaining the PA functionalized PLR (PLR-PA) (**Fig. 1a**). **Fig. 1b** shows

137 the UV-vis spectra of the PLR and PLR-PA sheets with thickness of 0.1 mm. All the PCM sheets

138 showed a high transmittance of ~80% at the wavelength of 500-800 nm, which indicates the addition
139 of PA didn't change the PLR transparency remarkably.

140 Both PA and PLR (with a lot of α -CD rings) are polyhydroxy compounds. The hydrogen bond
141 interaction between PLR (both PEO and α -CD) and PA can make sure the good dispersion of PA in
142 the PLR matrix. PLR-PA30 was selected as a typical example for the PA dispersion analysis (**Fig. 1c**).
143 There is no significant PA aggregation, as further illustrated in **Fig. 1d**. The PA has good compatibility
144 with PLR and is easy to be dispersed in the PLR matrix, which can be directly proved by the EDX
145 results (**Fig. 1e**). The FTIR spectra are shown in **Fig. 1f**. There is no obvious difference among all the
146 FTIR curves.

147 In **Fig. 1g**, the two significant peaks at 2θ angles of about 19° and about 23° are attributed to the (120)
148 and (032) planes, respectively. The crystallinity ($\varphi_c\%$) were calculated by the **Eq. 4**: [36]

$$149 \quad \varphi_c\% = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\omega_i \Delta H_m^0} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

150 where, ΔH_m (J g^{-1}) represented the measured enthalpies of melting, ΔH_m^0 (J g^{-1}) was the melting
151 enthalpy for a 100 % crystalline PEO and ω_i was the fraction of the component i in the sample. The
152 ΔH_m^0 of PEO was 196.4 J g^{-1} . [37] The results were listed in **Table S1**. We found that with the increase
153 of PA content, the crystallinity of the material decreased slightly. However, it can be maintained at
154 about 50%, which is also a prerequisite to ensure that the material has phase change thermal regulation.

155 *3.2 Mechanical performance*

156

157

158 **Fig. 2.** (a) full range stress-strain curves, (b) stress-strain curves at low strain region, (c) yielding strength,

159 (d) Young's moduli, (e) tensile strength, (f) elongation at break of the PCM samples, (g) boat-shape folded

160 sample, (h) twisted sample, (i) stretched sample and (j) hydrogen bond (the red dotted line) illustration

161 between PA and both PEO chain and α -CD ring.

162

163 Tensile test curves of the four PCM sheets are shown in **Fig. 2a**. The detailed values for the parameters

164 are summarized in **Table S2**. The samples show obvious yielding (**Fig. 2b**) and remarkable strain

165 hardening (Fig. 2a). It is found that the yielding strength (**Fig. 2c**), Young's modulus (**Fig. 2d**), and

166 tensile strength (**Fig. 2e**) of the materials increased at first and then decreased with the increase of PA

167 contents. The elongation increased steadily with the increase of PA contents. PLR-PA10 can reach the

168 top values for all the Young's Modulus (1527.4 MPa), tensile strength (24.0 MPa) and Yielding strength

169 (22.1 MPa). It is probably due to the excellent PA dispersion and the intramolecular hydrogen bond. It
 170 is clearly depicted in **Fig. 2g-i** that the samples can be easily deformable (twisting, folding, and
 171 stretching). As shown in **Fig. 2j**, the interactions between PA and α -CD may be hydrogen bond between
 172 α -CD in both PLR and PLRs. In addition, the oil-like additive can maintain the formability, which will
 173 benefit in the mechanical properties maintaining during tension.[32]

174 3.3 PCMs performance and shape memory properties

175 **Table 1.** Some core parameters of PCMs

Samples	ΔH_m (J g ⁻¹)	Enthalpy efficiency (%)	ΔE_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Extent of Supercooling (°C)	Heat lose (%)	Thermal conductivity (W m ⁻¹ k ⁻¹)	Form stability
PLR	88.6	99.9	571.1	10.0	2.1	0.28±0.03	No leakage
PLR-PA10	79.2	97.4	229.5	11.6	3.7	0.32±0.02	No leakage
PLR-PA20	68.3	89.5	475.9	15.3	1.4	0.34±0.04	No leakage
PLR-PA30	60.9	84.5	342.4	16.1	3.6	0.37±0.03	No leakage

176

177

178 **Fig. 3.** (a) DSC curves for second heating of PLR-PA10 with four different heating rates, (b) $\ln(\phi/T_p^2)-1/T_p$ plots;

179 (c) thermal conductivity results; (d) melting results of the PCMs; (e) DSC curves of PLR-PA10 after 100 times

180 thermal/cooling cycling; (f) the images of PLR-PA10 before and after thermal cycling test by DSC equipment;

181 form stability and leakage proof test of the PCMs: (g) 30 °C, and (h) 80 °C for 2 h, (i) Image of boat shape sample

182 PLR-PA10 before and after heat treatment, and (j) R_f and R_r values of the PCMs.

183

184 Kissinger equation was used to calculate the activation energy (ΔE_a , kJ mol⁻¹). Considering an

185 homogenous transformation at the phase change, the Kissinger equation reads [38],

$$186 \quad \frac{d[\ln(\phi/T_p^2)]}{d(1/T_p)} = -\frac{\Delta E_a(T)}{R} + T_p \ln\left(-\frac{AR}{E} f'(\alpha)\right) \quad (5)$$

187 where φ is the heating rate, T_p is the phase transition temperature. The detected T_p with different
188 heating rate are all listed in **Table S3**). A is the pre-exponential term in the Arrhenius kinetic, $f(\alpha)$ is
189 the transformation function at phase change and R is the gas constant. Typically, the Kissinger method
190 determines the activation energy considering the left-hand term and the first right-hand term in Eq. (5),
191 being then, the second right-hand term negligible. On a practical sound, this is acceptable provided the
192 quotient $\frac{\Delta E_a}{RT_p} > 10$, leading to an estimated modelling error below 2%. [39] In addition, this reflects
193 that the associated kinetic function rate of change in the proximity of the transformation is well
194 approximately constant. **Fig. 3a** shows the melting curves of PLR-PA10. The curves of samples PLR-
195 PA20 and PLR-PA30 are provided in Fig. S1-2. **Fig. 3b** presents the Kissinger plots. It is reported that
196 $\Delta E_{a,PLR}=571.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for PLR. [29] In current work, the following ΔE_a were obtained: $\Delta E_{a, PLR-}$
197 $PA10=229.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta E_{a, PLR-PA20}=475.9 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, and $\Delta E_{a, PLR-PA30}=342.4.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for PLR-PA10%,
198 PLR-PA20% and PLR-PA30%, respectively. We found that all the ΔE_a of the PLRs are much lower
199 than that of neat PLR, which is probably because the PA will promote the mobility process of PEO in
200 the PCMs. For each ΔE_a obtained, the quotient $\frac{\Delta E_a}{RT_p} > 10$ which permits the use of the Kissinger
201 equation (2) disregarding the kinetic term.

202 The extent of supercooling (ΔT , °C) can be calculated by **Eq. 3**:

$$203 \quad \Delta T = T_{m,onset} - T_{s,onset} \quad (6)$$

204 The calculated ΔT is summarized in **Table 1**. The ΔT increased slightly with the increase of PA
205 contents, indicating that the high PA contents will hinder the nucleation process of PEO chain. **Eq. 7**
206 was used to determine the Enthalpy efficiency of PCMs: [10, 40]

$$207 \quad \text{Enthalpy efficiency } \% = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\omega \Delta H_{PCM}} \times 100 \% \quad (7)$$

208 where, ΔH_m was the melting enthalpy of the PCMs. ΔH_{PCM} was the enthalpy of pure PLR, and ω
209 was the mass ratio of PLR in the PCMs.

210 The heat loss (η , %) can be calculated by **Eq. 8**:

$$211 \quad \eta = \frac{\Delta H_m - \Delta H_s}{\Delta H_m} \times 100 \% \quad (8)$$

212 where, ΔH_m ($J g^{-1}$) was the melting enthalpy, and ΔH_s ($J g^{-1}$) is solidification enthalpy. **Table 1** and
213 **Table S1** summarizes the thermal parameters of PLR and PLR-PAs, such as ΔH_m , $T_{m,onset}$, ΔH_s , and
214 $T_{s,onset}$. It is found that the thermal conductivity of the PCM increased slightly with the increase of PA
215 contents, the values of which were listed in Table 1 and shown in **Fig. 3c**. The PCMs exhibited a melting
216 enthalpy ($60.9\sim 79.2 J g^{-1}$, **Fig. 3d**) and high enthalpy efficiency. The corresponding DSC curves during
217 heating and cooling were provided in Figure S3-S6. Notably, according to **Eq. 8**, the heat loss for all
218 the samples is also listed in **Table 1**. All the η for PLR were quite low ($<3.7\%$), which indicated PA
219 will not significantly induce the heat dissipation for the PCMs. The PCMs films had high cycle
220 performance because the ΔH_m and ΔH_s , et al., were almost unchanged (**Fig. 3e** and **Table 1**). DSC
221 test sample has excellent shape retention after 100 cycles (**Fig. 3f**), indicating it is suitable for long-
222 term application stably.

223 The photos of PLR and PLR-PAs before and heat treatment are shown in **Fig. 3 g** and **Fig. 3 h**. No
224 leakage neither shape change (Fig. 4i) was observed during the heating process even when the
225 temperature was much higher than the corresponding T_m , which indicates that the PLRs have excellent
226 form stability and leakage-proof performance. Furthermore, it is found the PCMs show outstanding
227 SMPs. The detail shape memory results are all listed in **Table S4**. Notably, the R_f is higher than 98 %
228 of the initial strain after unloading of the stress, and the recovery ratio (R_r) is higher than 95 % as shown
229 in **Figure 3j**.

230

231 3.4 Thermal stability, fire safety and application

232

233 **Fig. 4.** Combustion images of sample (a) PLR, (b) sample PLR-PA10, (c) TGA curves of all the PCM
234 samples, (d) char morphology of sample PLR, (e) char morphology of sample PLR-PA10, (f) char
235 morphology of sample PLR-PA20, (g) char morphology of sample PLR-PA30, (h) HRR curves of all
236 the PCMs, (i) THR curves of all the PCMs, and (j) LOI values of the PCMs.

237

238 The combustion process of the four samples were shown in **Fig. 4a-4b** and **Fig. S3**. As a control sample,
239 pristine PLR produced obvious dripping (at 6s, **Fig. 4a**). All the PA functionalized PCMs have a stable
240 char residue (**Fig. 4 b and Fig. S7**) and show no dripping. During combustion, no dripping may slow
241 down the fire spread to a certain extent, and accordingly improve the flame retardancy.

242 Subsequently, TGA results are recorded and presented in **Fig. 4c** and **Table S5**. As it can be seen, all
243 the modified PCMs typically underwent a two-step decomposition process. The weight loss near 200
244 °C is mainly due to PA decomposition. [41] It is clearly seen that all the functionalized PLRs
245 decomposes earlier in comparison with PA, which begins to decompose after 170 °C. The weight loss
246 in the first stage (170 ~ 220 °C) is due to the PA decomposition, which is in consistent with the report
247 that the earlier start of decomposition with a higher char residue is often found for samples with good
248 flame retardancy. [42] [43, 44]

249 CONE was further used to characterize the fire safety of the materials. **Fig. 4d** to **4g** present the char
250 morphology of sample PLR, PLR-PA10, RLR-PA20 and PLR-PA30. This is consistent with the change
251 trend of residue in TGA, that is, the residual carbon content increases with the increase of PA content.
252 Most importantly, the pHRR of PLRs decreased with the increase of PA content. For PLR-PA30, the
253 pHRR was decreased by 54.2 %, and THR decreased by 34.0 % than that of PLR. The change trend of
254 THR can be seen intuitively in **Fig. 4g**. The specific data are listed in **Table 2**. It is clear from the results
255 that the fire safety of the modified material is improved due to the decrease of both pHRR and THR
256 significantly. LOI and UL-94 tests were recorded and the results are shown in **Fig. 4j** and **Table 2**. With
257 the addition of 30 wt.% PA, the LOI values increased from 20.8% to 28.2% and the PCM reached a V-
258 0 rating for the UL-94 test. We can understand the flame retardancy mechanism based on the well
259 reported statement elsewhere. Typically, during the combustion, PA often acted as the acid source in the
260 flame retardant system. In addition, the PA generates many non-combustible gases, produces
261 phosphorus-containing free radicals, and captures the free radical ions in the system in the gas phase.
262 At the same time, a large amount of phosphorus in its structure can be used as a charring agent to
263 promote the formation of more stable carbon residue in the system.[45] Cyclodextrin in PLR will be

264 dehydrated and carbonized during combustion to produce a large amount of carbon residue.[46] As a
 265 physical barrier, the carbon layer effectively insulates the transmission of oxygen and heat and plays an
 266 essential role in the flame retardance of the condensed phase.

267 **Table 2.** The char residue, TGA and typical parameters for CONE test, UL-94 and LOI

Samples	Residue (%) by TGA	pHRR (kW m ⁻²)	THR (MJ m ⁻²)	LOI (%)	UL-94	Dripping
PLR	1.1	652	65.9	20.8	No rating	Yes
PLR-PA10	6.5	391	52.5	26.1	No rating	No
PLR-PA20	11.4	420	46.0	27.5	No rating	No
PLR-PA30	16.5	298	44.0	28.2	V0	No

268

269 **Table 3.** Thermal properties of as-prepared composite PCMs and recently bio-based fire safe PCM
 270 composites

Year	PCM compositions	Flexible	Bio-based	Flame Retardants	Latent heat (J g ⁻¹)	LOI increase (%)	pHRR decrease (%)	References
2019	Bio-char/Paraffin	No	Yes	-	25.2-92.1	-	-	[47]
2019	Bio-waste/Nature soy-wax or Golden soy-wax	No	Yes	-	19.4-21.1	-	-	[48]

Oilseed straw or Miscanthus								
2020	straw/n-dodecane or 1-dodecanol	No	Yes	--	54.1-90.5	-	-	[49]
2010	HDPE/Paraffin	Yes	No	Expanded graphite	68.3-81.5	N/A	-62.0%	[14]
2010	HDPE/Paraffin	Yes	No	Chlorinated paraffin	49.6-70.1	N/A	-61.2%	[50]
2021	PGI/PEG	No	Yes	APP	70.1-86.9	+21.4%	-36.1%	[5]
2022	PLR	Yes	Yes	PA	60.9-79.2	+35.6%	-54.2%	This work

271

272 Some PCM key parameters in some other reports are listed in **Table 3**. Through comparison, we found
 273 that the significant progress of this work is reflected in: (1) efficient and green fabrication by using
 274 water as the only solvent, (2) Biobased, flexible and smart nature of the PCMs (3) excellent flame-
 275 retardant performance. Therefore, the material is expected to be applied safely in the sustainable field
 276 of temperature control of flexible electronic devices.

277

278

279 **Fig. 5.** (a) The device stack structure and test process, (b) the image of real Solid-State Disk (SSD),
 280 Polypropylene (PP, with thickness of 2 mm) sheet and PLR-PA30, (c) IR images of the simulated
 281 devices, (d) the temperature increasing curves of the devices.

282

283 To evaluate the heat management of the PCM on the electronic devices, we designed a schematic
 284 structure (Fig. 5a). The insulation layer (with thickness of 5 mm), heating source, protecting sheet (PP),
 285 PCM (Fig. 5b), and the metal heatsink stacked together to prepare the simulated device. Fig. 5c shows
 286 the IR images of samples A and B. Based on the IR images, we can further measure the temperature
 287 tendency (Fig. 5d). Notably, the curve of each sample here is drawn based on the average values with
 288 3 parallel tests, which can ensure the repeatability of the data. As shown in Fig. 5d, during the heating,
 289 sample PLR-PA30 showed significantly better heat control state than that of both the blank samples
 290 and commodities. Typically, the temperature of the protecting part with PCM was obviously lower than
 291 that of blank sample. Furthermore, during the phase transition, the temperature difference gradually

292 appears and keep relatively constant at about 3.5 °C. We assigned that the difference is because of the
293 latent heat of PLR-PA30, which plays a key role in heat management.

294

295 4. CONCLUSIONS

296 PLR with different PA contents (10%-30%) were prepared by using a green physical blending method.

297 Compared with the pristine PLR, all the Young's modulus, tensile strength and yielding strength of the

298 PLR-PAs increased at first and then decreased with the increase of PA contents. Typically, the Young's

299 modulus, yielding strength and tensile strength of the PLR were 826.7 MPa, 14.2 MPa and 14.2 MPa,

300 respectively, and significantly increased to 1527.4 MPa, 22.1 MPa, and 24.0 MPa respectively, with the

301 addition of 10 wt.% of PA. Elongation (>783 %) for all modified PCMs was gradually increased with

302 the increase of PA contents. Thermal analysis shows that the fire safety of PLR is significantly improved.

303 Specifically, for the best sample PLR/PA30, the pHRR could decrease by 54.2 %, THR decreased by

304 34.0%; the char residual increased from 1.1% to 13.6 % and the LOI increased from 20.8% to 28.2%;

305 moreover, the stable char residual will be formed during combustion process. The PCMs showed high

306 shape-fixing ratio ($R_f > 98\%$) and recovery ratio ($R_r > 95\%$). Further with the excellent form-stability

307 and good cycle performances, the modified PLRs are therefore fire safe, ultra-flexible, sustainable, and

308 advanced PCMs for energy storage.

309

310 **Supporting Information.**

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